

Hypothetical Learning Trajectory in STEM Approach with Project-Based Learning Model to Improve Students' Mathematical Proficiency

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Abstract

The aims of this study were to describe the design of teaching and learning process of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) approach with the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model in improving students' mathematical proficiency on linear equations in one variable topic. This research uses design research methods with steps, namely a preliminary design, teaching experimental, and retrospective analysis. The data were obtained from 50 junior high school students in grade VII in student worksheets, observation sheets during research, mathematical proficiency test instrument in the form of essay that has been through expert, the result of the interview, documentation, and video recording. The research results showed that: (1) HLT in STEM approach with the PjBL model has an effect of developing students' mathematical proficiency; (2) the mathematical proficiency of junior high school students were in a high category with n-gain 0.79. The results of this study can be used as a basis for designing a local instruction theory linear equation in one variable on STEM approach with the PjBL model to develop junior high school student students' mathematical proficiency.

Keywords: *Distance Learning, Linear Equation in One Variable, Mathematical Proficiency, Project-Based Learning, STEM.*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is turning to learn usually done face-to-face in schools, into virtual distance learning from home. As a result of these changes, many students experience learning loss (Engzell, Frey, & Verhagen, 2021). Learning loss occurs due to the lack of facilities that support virtual learning, reduced learning hours and basic competencies learned by students, and less optimal learning done by students at home (Makarim, 2021). This impact decreases student learning outcomes so that if we continue to worry about students' abilities will continue to decline, especially in mathematics (McKinsey & Company, 2020).

The low math ability before the COVID-19 pandemic was already below the average math ability of other countries. This can be seen in the 2018 PISA results, which state that around 28% of students in Indonesia reach level 2 or higher in mathematics than the OECD average of 76%. About 1% of students have a level 5 or higher in math proficiency than the OECD average of 11% (OECD, 2019). With the change in learning mathematics to become virtual, which causes learning loss, students' math proficiency will decrease. Therefore, designing an optimal, efficient, and effective learning program that can develop students' proficiency, especially proficiency in mathematics in virtual learning.

One learning approach that can accommodate learning from home and improve math proficiency to minimize learning loss is the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) approach. STEM is a learning approach that provides students with experiences of how concepts of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics are integrated to develop processes, products, and a beneficial system (Ong & McLean, 2014). STEM learning will be suitable to collaborate with the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) learning model to learn by doing hands-on activities. PjBL is a learning model designed to allow students to develop knowledge and skills through real-world related projects. The integration of STEM and PjBL makes it possible for students to actualize knowledge from various fields in STEM by doing projects in their learning. STEM-PjBL integration has been researched and proven its effectiveness is used in learning science and mathematics, but mostly only focuses on the ability to think creatively, think critically, self-efficacy, and other abilities of (Hanif, Wijaya, & Winarto, 2019); (Sumarni & Kadarwati, 2020); (Samsudin, Jamali, & Zain, 2020), no one has discussed to develop math proficiency. Therefore, researchers are interested in exploring STEM integration with PjBL to develop students' mathematical proficiency.

Mathematical proficiency is a person's mathematical ability that can be used and applied in various fields. A major component of mathematical proficiency is understanding, using, and relating mathematics to everyday life (Milgram, 2010). The five components of mathematical proficiency, namely (1) conceptual understanding, namely understanding of mathematical concepts, operations, and relationships; (2) procedural fluency, namely the skills to carry out procedures

flexibly, accurately, and efficiently; (3) strategic competence, namely the ability to formulate and solve mathematical problems; (4) adaptive reasoning, namely logical thinking, reflection, explanation, and justification; and (5) productive disposition, namely the habit of seeing mathematics as sensible, useful, and beneficial, coupled with self-confidence and persistence in learning. Mathematical proficiency describes aspects of expertise, competence, and knowledge and makes it necessary for anyone to be successful in learning mathematics (Kilpatrick, Swafford, & Findell, 2001). Therefore, mathematical proficiency is important to develop in a person, especially in learning mathematics.

One of the materials in mathematics that is still low in mathematical proficiency is the material for linear one-variable equations. This can be seen from the many learning barriers students learn in learning the material of one-variable linear equations. One variable obstacle for students in learning linear equations material includes ontogenic obstacles, namely a jump in students' thinking from arithmetic to algebraic thinking patterns; epistemological obstacles are found because of limited context. Therefore, to overcome these obstacles and to develop mathematical proficiency students, learning must be designed that can facilitate students who cause errors in doing questions, and the didactical obstacle is found because the teacher's teaching is procedural so that the formation of material concepts does not go well (Rohimah, 2017). To overcome these learning obstacles, teachers must anticipate the emergence of problems in learning by facilitating student learning trajectories. The teacher can anticipate student learning trajectories by developing a Hypothetical Learning Trajectory (HLT). HLT consists of three components, namely learning objectives, activities, and the learning hypothesis (Cobb et al., 2003).

Based on the above background, the researcher wanted to produce the hypothetical learning trajectory in STEM approach with PjBL that can develop math proficiency, especially in the subject of linear equation in one variable. The sequence of learning steps with the STEM approach with PjBL in this study is as follows.

Table 1. Integration of STEM approach with PjBL to develop mathematical proficiency

No.	Steps	Activities	Mathematical Proficiency Component
1.	Determining the problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning begins with determining the problem contextually, interestingly, and based on topics that are in accordance with real-world realities. Determination of the problem can be done by asking essential questions that can give assignments to students in finding the problem. The learning process at this stage can be done synchronously through zoom meetings, or google classroom, or other applications that support all students face-to-face online. 	Conceptual understanding
2.	Designing a plan	The design of the plan was carried out collaboratively online between teachers and students discussing the rules of the game in learning, selecting activities that support students to learn STEM from home, and integrating various possible subjects.	Procedural fluency
3.	Schedule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers and students collaborate online to schedule learning activities. The schedule includes making timelines, deadlines, guiding and reminding students, and asking students to make explanations of the projects they have made. 	Strategic competence
4.	Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring students both during synchronous learning and student activities in designing asynchronous projects. Monitoring asynchronously can be done, one of them is by chatting on WhatsApp Groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conceptual understanding Procedural fluency Strategic competence Adaptive reasoning

5. Test Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment is carried out to measure the achievement of standards in evaluating the progress of each student and providing feedback. • In testing these results, the teacher should make an online assessment rubric that can be made, for example with Google Forms so that students can show the results of their projects by uploading them to Google Forms and filling out some questions in order to test the results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conceptual understanding • Procedural fluency • Strategic competence • Adaptive reasoning
6. Experience Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers and students reflect on the activities and project results that have been carried out. • Reflection is done synchronously. • Students express their feelings and experiences during carrying out activities and completing projects. • Teachers and students discuss to improve performance during the learning process, so that new findings are found to answer the problems posed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptive reasoning • Productive disposition

METHOD

The invitations distributed to students who took part in this study were approximately 200 students, but only 62 students joined. Of the 62 students, the data were reliable for analysis as many as 50 students. All students who participated in this study had received approval from their parents/guardians that their children could be the sample in this study. The sampling technique was taken using random sampling at one of the junior high schools in Bandung. Data were gathered from the results sheet of student work, mathematical proficiency test results, teacher and student observation sheets, documented video recording, and interviews with students.

This research is an educational design research method. The steps of educational design research are a preliminary design, experimental, and retrospective analysis (Akker, Gravemeijer, McKinney, & Nieveen, 2006); (Plomp & Nieveen, 2013). In preliminary design, Researchers designed STEM-PjBL teaching materials based on students' 'hypothetical learning trajectories, which were arranged in such a way as to anticipate learning obstacles and be able to develop students' mathematical proficiency. Before the teaching materials are used in the experiment, they are validated by an expert. In addition, at this stage, the researcher made mathematical proficiency test questions and was validated by experts and was also tested on 80 randomly selected eighth-grade students who had studied material on the one variable linear equation. At the experimental stage, the learning devices compiled at the preliminary design stage were used in the experiment to see the effectiveness of the devices compiled. The experimental stage was carried out using synchronous and asynchronous learning. Synchronous learning uses online video meetings and asynchronous learning with the messenger group platform. Furthermore, at the retrospective analysis stage, all data that had been collected in the experiment stage were analyzed on the effectiveness of the teaching materials used, the questions given, the suitability of the hypothetical learning trajectory with the actual condition of the students in the experiment, and making reference in the revision of teaching materials for the next.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary Design

The preliminary design results from the initial learning design aim to implement STEM approach tools with the PjBL model by reviewing the literature, analyzing instructional videos, and analyzing school textbooks. Furthermore, several experts have tested the learning device that has been prepared for face validity and content validity. The results of the expert validation test were analyzed using the Q-Cochran statistic. It was found that the weighers considered each description of the learning device uniformly with a Q-Cochran value of 6.667.

Furthermore, the mathematical proficiency test questions were tested on VIII grade students, and the results were analyzed using the questioned validity, question reliability, difficulty level, and distinguishing power. From these results, 5 questions were taken that met the valid, reliable level of difficulty and good distinction.

The STEM approach is an approach that combines and links four fields of science, namely science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. The combination of STEM learning with the PjBL model can develop students' mathematical proficiency because students are trained to create learning based on problems of everyday life so that they can apply mathematics in various fields in STEM. The steps for learning the STEM-PjBL are starting from determining problems, designing plans, compiling schedules, monitoring, testing results, and evaluating experiences. The innovation in STEM-PjBL learning is that students can try something new, learn online with all variations, the collaboration between teachers and parents, the role of parents is greater in accompanying children, teachers facilitate in assisting the student learning process, and teachers monitor student learning activities regularly. Online. Thus, STEM approach with the PjBL model is one of the online learning innovations that can prepare students to face the challenges of 21-st century learning. Hypothetical learning trajectory in the application of linear equations in one variable using the STEM approach with PjBLmodel can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Example of HLT in the Application of a One-Variable Linear Equation

Learning objectives	Learning Trajectory	Learning Hypothesis
<p>Students can solve everyday problems related to linear equations of one variable</p>	<p>Application of the concept of a single variable linear equation with a dynamo powered car simulation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science: Measurement of displacement, distance, time, and velocity; • Technology: Use of the internet to search for information related to learning materials and computers or mobile phones to conduct synchronous learning. • Engineering: Design of dynamo powered car toy. <p>Students perform a dynamo powered car toy simulation by measuring the distance, time, and travel speed.</p> <p>Students draw a graph of the relationship between speed and distance or speed and time which will produce a one-variable linear equation.</p> <p>Teacher: What are the similarities of the graphs that have been made?</p> <p>Student 1: $x - 1 = 0$</p> <p>Teacher: any other answers?</p> <p>Student 2: $y - 2 = 0$</p> <p>Furthermore, other groups of students answered with various linear equations of one variable from the measurement results, either in the form of x or y variables.</p>	<p>Students can recognize the application of the concept of a single variable linear equation in everyday life and can improve students' mathematical proficiency.</p>

Teaching Experiment

The teaching experiment is intended to implement learning designs that have been created and validated at the preliminary design stage. At this stage, the learning design is implemented in one class to see the quality of the designs that have been compiled and to see the students' mathematical proficiency achievements. The study was carried out in four meetings. Each meeting discussed the meaning of closed sentences, open sentences, and equations, solving one-variable linear equations, solving one-variable linear equations in fraction form, and applying one-variable linear

equations. Student activities in carrying out learning with the STEM approach with the PjBL model can be seen in the application of the concept of a one-variable linear equation in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Learning Activities using STEM Approach with PjBL Model

In Figure 1 above, in Figure 1a, students design a dynamo powered car toy, then carry out a simulation as in Figure 1b and fill in the results of their observations and present them in class as in Figure 1c. One of the answers of a group of students that describes the relationship between velocity and distance is as follows:

Figure 2. Dynamo powered car toy simulation results

To see the effect of using learning designs in developing mathematical proficiency, a paired sample t-test is used. The paired sample t-test showed a significant effect on the use of learning designs in developing students' mathematical proficiency with an average pretest of 34.80 and an average posttest of 84.60. A correlation between pretest and posttest of 30%. Furthermore, because there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test, we will look for an increase in both of them with the normalized n-gain formula. The pretest and post-test scores of students' mathematical proficiency are then calculated to determine the rate of increase in the results of STEM approach with the PjBL model on linear equation in one variable topic. The summary of the results of the Average Gain Score analysis on the results of students' mathematical proficiency tests is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 2. The Result of Gain Score Analysis of Pre-test and Post-test Scores of Students' Mathematical Proficiency

Mean of Gain Score	Criteria
0,79	High
N-Gain Value	Category
$g > 0,70$	High
$0,30 \leq g \leq 0,70$	Medium
$g < 0,30$	Low

Table 2 shows that the average gain score in the experimental class shows the results of 0.77 in the high category.

Retrospective Analysis

Retrospective analysis is a comparative analysis between the learning designs designed at the preliminary design stage and the data obtained in the teaching experiment. The description of the activities carried out during the lesson to develop

mathematical proficiency is explained as follows. At the first meeting, students could carry out the project on the first student worksheet quite well. Some students had difficulty measuring the distance they traveled to walk because the house wall blocked the route. Overall, students can determine, make examples, and write down the meaning of open sentences and closed sentences. Students analyzed the video and images presented at the second and third meetings to find understanding and solve a one-variable linear equation. At the four, students were given problems to solve the linear equation of one variable in the form of a fraction. The five students made a car project to see the application of the linear one variable equation. Overall, students can learn well, but the obstacles for some students are unsupported internet signals.

The results of data analysis indicate that the application of the STEM approach design with the PjBL model can develop students' mathematical proficiency. These findings support and complement the findings (Priatna, Martadiputra, & Lorenzia, 2019) that STEM with the PjBL model can improve student learning outcomes. Learning with STEM approach begins with providing projects presented in student activities. after the teacher provides sufficient guidance, students can do projects at home. They have virtual discussions with their group of friends. The teacher checks virtually on groups of students to monitor and guide students who are experiencing difficulties, and then the student's work is presented in a class video meeting. Through projects, group discussions, teacher guidance, and class discussions, students can construct or discover mathematical concepts, principles, or procedures.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that STEM approach with the PjBL model applied to a linear equation in one variable topic can improve students' mathematical proficiency. The effectiveness of the STEM-PjBL model can be seen from the significant mean difference between pretest and posttest and scores n-gain 0,79 with the high effect category. It can be developed better and can develop children's math skills so that at least for mathematics teachers (the Ministry of Education or the group of MGMP/policymakers) they can provide/be held a STEM-PjBL training which focuses on mathematics, mostly now in junior high school focus to science so that mathematics is less highlighted. You can add a STEM course to the secondary curriculum for the junior high school department to learn and design STEM learning before becoming mathematics teachers.

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